

PAKISTAN LIBRARY BULLETIN

Vol. XI

March - June 1980

No. 1-2

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Subscription Rates:—

Inland: Annual	Rs. 35.00	Foreign: Annual (Air Mail)	\$ 12.00
		Single copy:	\$ 5.00
Students:	Rs. 25.00	
		Single copy:	Rs. 12.00

Printed by Mr. M. K. Usmani at the Technical Printers, Koocha Haji Usmani,
Near Bombay Hotel, I. I. Chundrigar Road, Karachi.

The Royal Library Of Bijapur

Saleemuddin Qureshi*

About two hundred and forty miles south-east of Bombay lie the remains of the capital of the Adil Shahi dynasty, Bijapur*. Founded by Yusuf Adil Shah in 1489 AD, the kingdom survived until 1686 AD, when the last of his eight¹ successors, Sikandar Adil Shah was defeated by Aurangzeb and his territory annexed to the Mughal Empire. In spite of this relatively short rule of about two hundred years, during which the kingdom was constantly threatened by internal and external forces, the dynasty made an important contribution to Muslim culture in India. Bold experiments were made in the fields of arts, architecture, religion, and literature. Ibrahim Adil Shah I was the first king in India to introduce Urdu² as the official language of his court, when it was still in its infancy. The architectural excellence of its mosques, palaces, minarets, tombs, and cisterns rivalled those of the mighty Mughals in Delhi.

Among the remains of these buildings in Bijapur is the Asar Mahall, which once housed the Royal Library of the Adil Shahi Kings, the residue of which was transferred to the India Office Library in 1953.

Very little is known about the origin, or the contents of this library in its earlier stages but acquisition notes on some of the manu-

* India Office Library, London.

scripts now preserved in the India Office Library indicate that a Royal Library [Kitabkhanah-i ma'murah] was in existence in Bijapur in 880 AH/1475 AD, when the city was part of the Bahmani sultanate. Similar notes, official stamps, seals, and signatures of previous owners, including those of Ibrahim Adil Shah II, Muhammad Adil Shah, and other kings of this dynasty indicate that a large number of these manuscripts were acquired by the Adil Shahi kings between 992 AH/1584 AD, and 1055 AH/1645 AD. Some of these manuscripts had previously belonged to the Royal libraries of Shah Jahan, Aurangzeb Alamgir, Sultan of Golkandah Quli Qutb Shah, and the Bahmani kings of Bidar, while the others reached Bijapur from distant places like Samarqand, Bukhara, Shiraz, and Mecca. The Library seems to have flourished under the rule of Ali Adil Shah, and his successor Ibrahim Adil Shah II. Ali Adil Shah was a great patron of the arts, and literature. Bijapur became a centre of learning during his reign. Mulla Nusrati, Ayyaghi, Mirza Hashimi, Shah Amin al-Din A'la are some of the poets who had assembled in his court. The Sultan himself was a distinguished poet in his own right. Rafi' al-Din Shirazi who served the Adil Shahi dynasty for about twenty one years gives an eye-witness account of Ali Adil Shah's love of reading and his collection of books. In his Tazkirat al-muluk he wrote :³

He used to keep his favourite books in four boxes, which he used to keep with him during his journey, as well as when he was in his palace. Once on a journey, when he was near his destination, it started to rain, and the rivers flooded, and it became difficult to cross them. In these circumstances the army became dispersed. When he reached his destination he realised that the boxes of books were no longer with him. It was discovered, later on, that the boxes had gone with the Royal Treasury by some other route, and the people who were looking after them had stayed behind. He became very angry, exclaiming that he had told them a thousand times that the boxes should not be separated from him under any circum-

tances, but to no avail. One of the nobles was at once sent to collect these boxes, and the Sultan did not rest until they were brought to him.

As regards to the contents, and the size of the Royal Library during this period, Shirazi wrote :⁴

The Sultan was very fond of books, and reading. He had collected numerous books relating to all types of subjects, so much so that his library had become completely full of books. He had employed nearly sixty people, including calligraphers, gilders, book-binders, and illuminators, who were busy all day in looking after these books in the library. Considering that such a large number of people were employed to look after this collection, the library must have been a large, and prestigious institution during this period. This is also evident from what seems to be a large salary paid to the Librarian of this library. P. M. Joshi,⁵ in his article, Ali Adil Shah I of Bijapur, and his royal librarian : two ruq 'as' has reproduced two documents which were issued by the council of ministers of Ali Adil Shah to a Hindu scholar Sis Vaman, son of Anant, as a warrant of his appointment as a librarian, in charge of the Royal Library of Bijapur.

The first document, dated Rabi, II, 975 AH/October 1567 AD gives his annual salary as 1,000 Hun. (A Hun at that time was roughly equal to 3.50 rupees, making his annual salary 3,500 rupees per annum.) The second document, dated 1 Safar 983 AH/May 1575 AD, merely confirms his appointment, and his salary. Although the title of Pandit added to his name showed some recognition of his scholarship, but, even after eight years his salary remained the same. In addition to the Royal Library, which in the above mentioned two documents has been described as Kitabkhanah [library], and Mahall kitabkhanah [the Palace Library] respectively, each king seems to have maintained his personal library as well.

An inscription on the title page of a commentary on al-Lubab (Loth 898), for example, indicates that it was captured at Bidar, and entered in the library of Ibrahim 'Adil Shah II on 12 Sha'ban, 1027 AH/July 1618 AD. Another library, which seems to have existed in Bijapur during this period, and from where some of the manuscripts were later transferred to the Asar Mahall library was Qadiriya Library. It most probably belonged to the mausoleum of Shaikh Hamid Qadiri—a Muslim saint who lived in Bijapur during the reign of Ibrahim Adil Shah II.

During this period the Royal Library must have been housed in one of the other palaces, as the Asar Mahall, as we know it today, was not built until 1646 AD.⁶

According to Zubairi⁷ it was originally built as Dad Mahall, or the Hall of Justice, and in the beginning used as such, but later on, because of its association with the relics which were preserved there it came to be known as Asar Mahall. According to Farishtah's the relics were brought to Bijapur by a sufi saint Mir Muhammad Salih Hamdani in 1005 AH/1596 AD.⁸ However, according to Zubairi⁹ these were already there in Bijapur in 1000 AH/1591 AD when a sufi saint Shah Sibghat Allah was taken by Ibrahim Adil Shah II to Asar Mahall to pay homage to these relics. Elsewhere, however Zubairi contradicts this statement by saying that :¹⁰

In 1056 AH/1646 AD the Gagan Mahall was destroyed by fire, and in the same year Muhammad 'Adil Shah built another palace called Dad Mahall, decorated with various colours and designs, and nowadays, the relics of the Prophet Muhammad are preserved there, and people come to pay homage to these relics.

Bashir al-Din Ahmad¹¹ has offered a likely explanation for these apparently contradictory statements. According to him the relics were first preserved in Gagan Mahall (built in 1561 AD), and when

in 1056 AH/1646 AD it was destroyed by fire, these were transferred to the newly built Asar Mahall. The earlier references to Asar Mahall by Zubairi, according to Bashir al-Din Ahmad,¹² most probably refer to Gagan Mahall.

The building of Asar Mahall, which stands on the brink of a large tank, consists, according to M.A. Frere¹³, of a great hall enclosed on three sides, and open only to the east, on which side the roof was supported by lofty wooden columns of great size, between which formerly hung enormous screens of rich cloth, falling like the drop-scene of a theatre. The hall occupies the entire height of the building, so as to form in fact, a gigantic veranda, occupying the whole length of the pile, and about half its width. Dr. Bird¹⁴ states it as 120 by 35 feet, and its height is in full proportion to its length.

Zubairi¹⁵ has also mentioned the appointment of two teachers by Muhammad Adil Shah in the Asar Mahall, indicating that the building was used as a theological school for Muslims during this period. Large assignments of land, and revenue were made available for the support of this establishment by Muhammad Adil Shah.

It is during this period that the library was, most probably moved from its earlier home to the Asar Mahall, and where it seems to have continued to function until 1686 AD. After the conquest of Bijapur by Aurangzeb the collection, as the seals, and inscription on the manuscripts indicate, was examined by Qabil Khan, a nobleman of Aurangzeb Alamgir.

According to Henry Cousens¹⁶, bulk of the manuscripts from this collection were 'carted away' by Aurangzeb at this stage. The same statement, again without citing any references has been repeated by Muhammad Zubairi¹⁷ in his 'Islami Kutubkhane'. There are, however a number of factors which seem to contradict these statements.

First of all, after the conquest of Bijapur, Aurangzeb most of his remaining life stayed in Deccan, and is buried there. These manuscripts would have been more useful to him in Deccan, rather than in Delhi.

Moreover, there are a number of manuscripts present in this collection which formerly belonged to the Royal Library of Aurangzeb, and which were later on transferred to the Asar Mahall Library. For example, 10L Loth 198, 676, 739, 901 and 1035 all have seals or notes of Alamgir, or his servants dated between 1069 AH/1658-59 AD, and 1079 AH/1668-69 AD, indicating that these manuscripts were required by the Royal library of Bijapur sometime after these dates.

It also seems strange that Aurangzeb, who had commissioned the compilation of the famous work on Islamic law of this period, *Fatava-i-Alamgiri*; and who himself was an acknowledged scholar of Islamic law, and theology could have ignored some of the most rare, and unique works, like Sayyid Sharif Jurjani's commentary on *Kitab al-mavaqiffi ilm al-kalam*, by Azud al-Din Iji (10L Loth 438), and Jalal al-Din Rumi's *Fihi ma fihi* (10L Persian Ethe 3063) which are still present in this collection.

Another factor that seems to contradict this notion is the Mughal Library of Delhi, the contents of which were acquired by the British Government after the fall of Delhi in 1857. None of the manuscripts in this collection, now known as the Delhi collection in the India Office Library could be traced to carry any indication that it had previously belonged to the Asar Mahall Library.

The territory of Bijapur remained annexed to the Mughal Empire until 1724 AD, when Nizam al-mulk, the Governor of Deccan proclaimed his independence. The library was, at this stage inspected by the orders of the commander of the Asaf Jah's forces by Muhammad Akram al-Mizli, and Abd Allah ibn Zain. Most of the manuscripts in this collection carry notes and seals to this effect.

The library, as the addition of a number of manuscripts to the collection, including a copy of Ibn Arabi's Kitab al-alam, (IOL Loth 695), dated 1143 AH/1730 AD, and a copy of Sharh al-nikat (IOL Ethe 3070), dated 1138 AH/1725 AD indicate was still functioning until 1760, when the Nizam of Hyderabad was forced to cede this territory to the Maratha Sardar Peshwa. It is during this period that the library, along with the other buildings seems to have suffered severely. According to Henry Cousens,¹⁸ 'it was under the Marathas [that] the city suffered severely. They found in its public buildings a mine of material which they immediately proceeded to appropriate. The palaces were stripped of all their wood; beams, doors, windows were ruthlessly torn out and carted away'.

After the fall of the Peshwa in 1818, Bijapur came under the British administration, and the territory was assigned to the Raja of Satara.

The library, or what was left of it by then was completely neglected during this period, until 1841-42, when it was visited by Mr. C. D'Ochoa, a French subject of Spanish origin who was deputed by the French Government to procure literary and scientific works from this part of the world. Reporting on the state of the library, and the efforts of D'Ochoa to preserve it, Mr. H.B.E. Frere,¹⁹ Commissioner of Satara, in his letter dated 17 December 1846 to the Chief Secretary, Government of Bombay, observed that :

Monsieur D'Ochoa drew the attention of Colonel Ovens to the State of the manuscripts, and assisted by the Residents' influence with the Raja, was allowed to examine them, and arrange them so far as to separate the more perfect manuscripts, from those which were utterly destroyed; and it is, I believe, principally owing to him that the destruction of the library has not been more complete.'

D'Ochoa also compiled a list of these manuscripts, a copy of which was later sent to Colonel Ovens. However, after the departure of

D'Ochoa the library seems to have suffered from further neglect and plundering. Later on the Bombay Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society alerted the attention of the Government of Bombay regarding their condition, and the importance of these manuscripts. It also wished that the collection should be made available to the scholars.

On the orders of the Raja, two lists-one in Persian, and the other in Marathi, of 430 manuscripts were prepared and sent to the Chief Secretary to the Government of Bombay. A copy of the Persian list was also sent to the Bombay Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society. Each volume was then, on the orders of the Raja wrapped in a cloth, its title ticked on the covering, and inspections of these manuscripts by responsible persons, at regular intervals arranged to safeguard them from further damage.

After the death of the Raja in 1848, and in the absence of any heir, the territory of Satara came under the direct rule of the Bombay Presidency. A year later, in 1849 Mr. Malet, Chief Secretary to Government of Bombay asked Mr. Frere, Commissioner of Sarata to submit a report on the condition, and the value of these manuscripts. Describing the condition of the manuscripts during this period Mr. Frere wrote:²⁰

'As it is, there are baskets, and boxes of half-eaten binding and fragments of leaves, hardly admitting of identification, and other wreck of destroyed volumes equalling, if not exceeding in bulk, the more perfect remains. There appears, also, every reason to believe that many of the more ornamental, if not the more valuable volumes, have disappeared bodily, during the last thirty or forty years, clandestinely sold by the needy custodians of the building, or by rapacious Government servants, who had access to the neglected treasures of this library'.

At this time the library was located in a small room on the ground floor, near the staircase. Mr. Frere²¹ described this room as, 'a small

apartment, fitted up with shelves, divided into cupboards, in which the books were formerly arranged ; but the white-ants had found their way through the walls in various directions, and the books are now kept in boxes'.

Mr. Frere²² engaged the services of Hakim Hamid al-Din, whom he described as 'a very accomplished Arabic scholar', and 'a Mahomedan gentleman of great respectability, and of reputed skill as a physician' to catalogue this collection. He was a native of Hyderabad, and had worked as a physician on the Raja's household establishment. With the help of two inamdars, and three or four writers, who were there to help him in reading, extracting, and writing the catalogue from his dictation, as he himself was a cripple from his birth, Hakim Hamid al-Din prepared a 'catalogue raisonnee' of these manuscripts in Urdu.

The catalogue, together with the report was sent to Mr. Malet by Mr. Frere. Hakim Hamid al-Din received. Rs. 300, a shawl, and some Persian and Arabic books as a reward for his labour.

As far as the future of these manuscripts was concerned, Mr. Frere²³ recommended that 'should any of them prove to be especially worthy the notice of scholars, I would suggest that they be removed either to Bombay, or to the library of the Honorable Court of Directors at the India House, as the provision for their safe custody at Bijapur is not so sure as could be wished, and they are there useless to the poverty-stricken and unlettered inhabitants, and out of the way, and very difficult of access to learned strangers'.

Captain L.W. Hart.²⁴ in charge of the Satara Residency had earlier advised the Government against such a move, arguing that :

'It would be the cause of the greatest dissatisfaction to the Musalman population to remove any of them from Bijapur'.

Whilst acknowledging this possibility Mr. Frere suggested that :²⁵

'Any real scruples, or superstitious fears they might entertain would probably be removed by coupling the removal of the books with the repair of the roof, and the renewal of the great beam which is giving way. Any volumes which might not be valuable or curious might be left where they are; and if the Government would supply the place of the volumes removed with a set of Arabic, Persian, and Hindee books, published by, or on behalf of the Government, and of which many copies are probably mouldering in the Government stores at Bombay, and Calcutta, the poor Mahomedans would be better reconciled to the measure, and the foundation might be laid of a library, which hereafter might be useful, and as much used by the modern inhabitants of the city as the old library was by their ancestors.'

The case was referred to Mr. Erskine, Deputy Secretary to Government in the Persian Department, who was asked to advise the Government about the value and importance of this collection. From Hakim Hamid al-Din's catalogue; Mr. Erskine prepared a list of these manuscripts in Roman characters. The list was later inherited by Mr. Erskine's successor, Dr. Wilson. After studying the contents of this list, Dr. Wilson²⁶ advised the Government that 'the collection viewed as a whole, is one of considerable value. Its special interest, however lies in its containing the body of the works which formed the fountain of authority in religion and law to the Bijapur dynasty, probably from its formation in A.D. 1489, to its expiration in A.D. 1672.'

He also recommended that the entire collection should be sent to the Court of Directors, 'who may perhaps, be inclined to preserve it as it now stands, or to distribute such of the volumes as it may not require among the public libraries of Europe'.

On his advice the entire collection, with the exception of a copy of Zobur, which was donated to the British and Foreign Bible Society

was, in March 1853 sent to the Court of Directors for deposit in the India Office Library.

Here, in 1869, it was examined by a well known Arabic poet, scholar, and calligrapher, Mr. Rizk Allah Hassoun Effendi.²⁷ He had earlier lived in Constantinople, Cairo, Damascus, and St. Petersburg, where he claims to have examined various Arabic manuscript (MSS.) collections, and had now come to London in search of some rare manuscripts (MSS.) While in London he published a number of Arabic works, including 'Ash'ar al-shi'r a metrical Arabic translation of Book of Job, Diwan Hatim Ta'i, al-Nafathat, and an Arabic journal on politics, Mir'at al-ahval, which was published from London in 1877, and was most probably the first Arabic journal issued from this country.

Mr. Hassoun²⁸ was introduced to Dr. Hall, the Librarian of the India Office Library, by Mr. Antonius Ameuney, Professor of Arabic, Kings College, Cambridge. Realizing the importance of these manuscripts, which he disclosed "I never saw before in my life such ancient and peerless MSS. in fact no where else to be found, on the face of the globe", and the need for these to be known to the outside world, he proposed to prepare a catalogue of this collection. It was completed in March 1869,²⁹ and while Sayyid 'Abd Allah, a lecturer in Hindustani at Kings College, Cambridge, and a friend of Mr. Hassoun was busy in translating this catalogue from the Arabic into English, a dispute arose between the Librarian, and Mr. Hassoun.

Mr. Hassoun seems to have given a lot of publicity to the fact that the manuscripts were being kept in a very poor condition in the Library.

This annoyed Dr. Hall, who in return threatened to terminate his engagement, and refused to pay his dues. Mr. Hassoun complained to the Under Secretary of State for India, stating that he was astonished to see that a librarian of a civilised government should be so

unbookish' as to ask him 'if the loose and scattered manuscripts were not of much use to throw them aside, and commence the catalogue of bounds works alone'. The dispute was resolved by Mr. Rost, who succeeded Dr. Hall in June 1869.

Mr. Hassoun's catalogue, now in the India Office Library, is a fine example of Naskh calligraphy, but it gives only minimum details about these works. For the manuscripts complete, and known MSS he gives author, title, dates, beginning and ends, and the colophon, while for incomplete, and known manuscripts only author, and title, and in a number of cases where the true identity of a work could not be ascertained, only a general title is given. The English translation of this catalogue, a copy of which was submitted to Dr Hall in April 1869 could not be traced in the library. Mr Hassoun, in his letters to the Under Secretary of State for India mentions the existence of a number of works in this collection which contained the seals, and signatures of Tamerlane. However no such works could be found in the library at present. It is possible that he may be referring to the three Kufic manuscripts of the Qura'n which Tamerlane is supposed to have brought from Damascus to India, and were acquired by the British Government from the heirs of Raja Ranjit Singe in 1859. However these works do not contain any seals, or signatures of Tamerlane.

Later on the task of arranging and identifying these manuscripts was given to Professor Ameeroney, who worked on these manuscripts for just over three months. His offer to catalogue this collection was declined, and instead Dr Loth, Professor of Arabic, Leipzig University was asked to undertake this task. Dr Loth commenced this work in Easter 1870, and completed it in August 1872. However because of the lack of indices, which were prepared by Dr. Loth in 1876, the catalogue could not be published until 1877.³⁰

It contains description of 1050 works, out of which 434 manuscripts are from Bijapur, and the rest from various other collections. The Bijapur manuscripts are identified in this catalogue by the prefix B

added to the accession number of the manuscript. These are given under the following subject headings :

Quran; Quranic sciences : 43 ; Traditions-26 ; Science of Traditions-4 ; Law, Hanafites-37 ; Law, Shafi' ites-9; Principles of Jurisprudence-24; Prayers and charms-16; Scholastic theology-56 ; Philosophy-48 : Sufism and Ethics-76; Biography and History-3; Mathematics and Astronomy-13; Medicine-2; Poetry-11 ; Rhetoric-20 ; Grammar-34 ; Dictionaries-5 ; Encyclopaedias-1; Miscellaneous-5.

As the above figures show, most manuscripts appear under Sufism and Ethic ; followed by Scholastic theology; and Islamic law. The absence of the copies of the Qur'an in the collection is rather surprising, when especially know that the library belonged to a theological school. One explanation for their absence may be the Muslim practice of burning and then burying the remains of any old and defective copy of the Qur'an in a well. As the whole collection was in a state of ruin, it is possible that the Mutavallis of this collection, may have weeded it of any old and defective copies of the Qur'an before it was acquired by the British government.

There are no works under History, Cosmography, Shi'ite law and Prosody in this Collection. The Number of works given under Biography and Medicine, two very popular subjects of this era is comparatively small, i.e. 3 & 2 respectively. The absence of any historical works in this library was noticed by J. Bird³¹ Ip. 1843, who in his article, 'The ruined of Bijapur reported that 'At the request of Lieut-Col. Briggs, the late Resident at Satara, Mr Kheirat Ali, commonly called Mushtak, the learned Persian Secretary of the Residency, made out a catalogue of the whole ; but no historical works were discovered.'

Most of the works in this collection were written or copied during the 9th and 10th century, of Hijrah, but there a number of works

belonging to 6th or 7th century. The earliest dated manuscript in this collection is a copy of the 4th volume al-Kasbaf, by Zamakshari (Loth 57). It was copied in 528 AH/1133 AD from the author's own autograph copy³² Another important work of this period is in autograph of al-Talvih by the famous gazi of Tamerlane, Sa'd al-Din Taftazani (Loth 322).

There are a number of works among the undated manuscripts which were written or copied during the 6th or 7th century of Hijrah. For example a copy of a commentary on Sayyid Nasir al-Din Abu'l-Qasim Muhammad bin Yusuf Samarqandi Madahi's 'al-Fiqh al-nafii, entitled al-Mustafi, by Abu'l-Barkat 'Abd Allah bin Ahmad Nasafi (Loth 208) was most probably transcribed by the Commentaror himself (died 711 A.H.) Similarly a copy of al-Hasil (Loth 292), which is an abridgement of Fakhr al-Din Razi's al-Mahsul, by Taj al-Din Abu'l-Faz'il Muhammad bin al-Hassan Urmavi seems to have been transcribed during the author's life time (died 656AH), and a copy of al-Hariri's Maqamat (Loth 809) was most probably transcribed during the 5th or 6th century of Hijrah.

The collection as a whole is not very rich in Calligraphy. The only notable exceptions in this case are : Loth 292, 299, 322, 325, 404, 418, 428, 438, 461, 503, 525, 526, 532, 872, 898, 901, 953, add 963.

'Abd al-Rahman bin Sulaiman, Muhammad bin Shihab Nur Allah Yazdi, Idris bin Hamzah bin Shu'aib Hanafi, Zain bin 'Abd Allah Munaibil, Abu Yusuf bin Baha al-Din Sighnaqi, Ibrahim bin 'Abd Allah, Muhammad bin Ahmad al-Shibli Hanafi. 'Abd al-Qadir bin 'Abd al-Malik, Muhammad 'Adil of Shaikhpurah, Mughis al-Din Muhammad Husain, 'Ata Allah bin Muhammad Husain Samarqandi, Muhammad bin Usman Kirmasti, Sayyid Zain al-'Abidin bin Sayyid 'Abd al-Vahhab Husaini, Ilyas bin Shaikh Farid of Fathpur-Sikri, and Mir Muhammad are some of the notable scribes of these manuscripts were copied in various parts of India

and other were written in far of places like Shiraz, Bukhara, Samarqand, Qaraman, Balkh, and Mecca.

Another surprising feature of this collection is the absence of works in the Urdu language and especially when we know that it was given official Patronage by Adil Shahi Kings.

The number of work in the Persian language in this collection is also very small. Only 17 manuscripts in Persian language were found in this Collection. These were described by Ethe³³ (Vol. 2, nos 3059-3076) under the following subject headings; Romances - 1; Poetry-1; Sufism-9; Astronomy-2; Interpretation of the Qur'an-1; Hinduism-1; Varia (Falmamah-i ja'far Sadiq, and 'Itriyah-iNauras Shahi)-2.

It includes a very unique copy of the extremely rare prose treatise on sufism, *Fihi ma fihi* by Maulana Jalal al-Din Rumi. Another important work in this collection is a very elaborate and extensive commentary on Ibn al'Arabi's famous mystic work, *Fusus al-Hakm*, by Rukn al-Din Shirazi.

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14. Bird, James. The ruined city of Bijapur. In Journal of the Bombay Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society. Vol. I. 1843. p. 382 Captain Philip D. Hart in his work, 'Architectural illustrations of the principal Mahometan buildings of Bijapur (London, 1859) gives the size of this building as only 135 feet North and South, by 100 feet East and West.
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16. Cousens, Henry. Bijapur and its architectural remains. Bombay, 1916. (Archaeological Survey of India Vol. 37). pp 90-92.
17. Zubair, Muhammad. Islami kutubkhane. Delhi, 1961. pp. 256-57.
18. Ibid. p. 91.
19. Selections. p. 216.
20. Selections. pp. 216-217.
21. Selections. p. 216.
22. Selections. p. 218.
23. Selections. p. 218.
24. Selections. p. 213.
25. Selections. p. 219.
26. Selections. p. 239.
27. The correct transliteration of his name, as given in the Catalogue of Arabic manuscripts is : Rizq Allah Ibn Ni'mat Allah Hassun. However, in his correspondence in English he has used the above form.
28. India Office Records. Financial Department. Home correspondence. L/F/2/ 350-632. 1869. Letter nos , 631-33.
29. Rizq Allah Hassun. [Catalogue of Bijapur collection]. India Office Library. Asabic manuscript I.O. 4719.